

Air Pollutant Measurement in Street from Roadside Tree Leaves through Regression Learning for Online Air Quality Index

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Abstract- In this paper, air quality is measured in streets through deposition of pollutant on tree leaves. The leaves from roadside investigated for various pollutant depositions such as NO₂, CO, OH and pollutant level is measured through satellite image. The roadside tree leaves is analyzed in high-resolution satellite images for pixel variations such as Hue, Saturation, Intensity due to deposition of pollutants on the leaf surface. The regression learning algorithms apply for prediction of pollutant levels from leaf images HSI and AQI values from Government lab. The above method provides the live measurement of air quality in streetwise and avoids the delay in lab measurements of pollutants. The live air quality measurements lead to awareness to the people and help the traffic department to divert the vehicles in low pollutant streets. From the results, the pollutant level on the street is validated through lab measurement, and the proposed method provides an accuracy of 85% of pollutant measurements from tree leaves from the satellite image.

I. INTRODUCTION

Air pollution is the global issue and occurs due to various sources such as industries, vehicles, wildfires and wind dust. The pollutant level varies from day to day and second to second and shortens the life span of people. A Human inhale 14kg of air every day. The inhaled air contains pollutants such as sulphates, carbons, nitrates, mineral dust, sodium chloride, nitrous oxide and ozone mixed with oxygen. World Health Organization (WHO) estimates, 92 percent of world's population breathe pollutant air and leads to major health effects such as Acquired Immune Deficiency Syndrome (AIDS), Tuberculosis (TB) and malaria. In India, 703 monitoring station network spread over urban areas to measure pollutant amount present in air on daily bases based on area and not on streetwise. The Thermo Gravimetry (TG)-FTIR is used to analyze pyrolysis process of willow trees. The evaluated result of pyrolysis reflects the good formation of CO, CO₂, hydrocarbons, alcohols and willow wood vinegar more effectively in an efficient manner. This effect has been widely studied by Zhen Liu et al. [1]. In some cases, ATR-FTIR technique and leaf cuticles as a base is used for evaluating stress response of leaf cuticles with respect to temperature variation. The above technique prevents the heat stress of tree species, Pisum Sativum studied by Na Liu et al. [2]. Open path FTIR is used during peak hours of traffic to identify behavior of ammonium sulphate with respect to seasonal changes. The evaluated ammonium sulphate is compared with ground values for correcting deviations due to seasonal variations given by Phillips et al. [3]. The impact of air pollution on roadside vegetation using physical mechanism dispersion and Large Eddy Simulation (LES) studied by Tong et al. [4]. The effects of dust particles on the leaf of selected tree species planted along the roadside and studied chlorophyll degradation, necrosis and photosynthesis reduction reported by Chaturvedi et al. [5]. The Spectro photometrical to measure dust deposition on leaves and investigate traffic relation. The photometrical measurements suggested to improve chlorosis, necrosis and

epinasty damages caused by air pollutants to plants is studied by Prusty et al. [6]. The scanning microscope and plasma-optical emission spectrometry by analysing effects of Particulate Matter (PM) in atmosphere and investigate elements such as carbon, oxygen, silicon, calcium, potassium, magnesium, lead, ferrous oxide, titanium and aluminium, to improve human health impacts by Feng Shao et al. [7]. The spectro radiometer is used to observe the variations in distribution and spectral characteristics of clusters of dust deposition on plant leaves with respect to atmospheric changes by Yan et al. [8]. The APTI is used to screen particular plant species contaminated by air pollutants by comparing the index values and susceptibility level of plants in air pollution, observed under laboratory and field experiments by Singh et al. [9]. The biochemical parameters, leaf morphology and enzyme activity is used by investigating air pollutant such as PM in roadside plants of indo-burma region. The above method investigates heavy metal concentrations for 12 common plants by Rai [10]. The sensitivity of plant leaves from tree species such as *Azadirachta* and *Mangifera indica* is analyzed to examine air pollutant using APTI parameter by Jain et al. [11].

A. *Related Work*

FTIR spectrometer is used for detecting different atmospheric chemicals in rotational and vibrational spectral bands, for overcoming limitations of the external radiation source of limb sounding observation scheme Bianchini et al. [12]. The distribution of polluted gases in the atmosphere is done using passive FTIR which provides quality 2D map image of air pollution at a fixed point in the atmosphere Fang et al. [13]. Gradient method is used to measure the vertical profile of trace gases and estimated surface fluxes using boundary method. The boundary method enables to monitor spatial and temporal average fluxes and improves measurement of nitrogen oxide and methane gases Griffitha et al. [14]. The slant path flux gradient (FG) combined with Open Path (OP)-FTIR spectroscopy techniques for quantifying gaseous emissions and measures the fluxes of NH_3 , NO_2 , CO_2 , and CH_4 using Multiple Atmospheric Layer Transmission (MALT) Baia et al. [15]. The entire atmospheric region of collected data using Gas Fitting (GFIT) code is covered and measured using detectors. The detector output predicts atmospheric ethene of column less than 1×10^{15} mole cm^{-2} by Toon et al. [16]. Ground based FTIR spectroscopy is used to increase altitude coverage of ozone in the atmosphere. The FTIR ground based method limits the usage of MW radiometry for low altitude measurement using Inversion technique and Optical Estimation Method (OEM) by Eriksson et al. [17]. The intensity, area and gross normalization of air pollution background from each factory is used along with meteorological and GIS using swam optimization algorithm to improve the accuracy level for predicting air pollution by Chen et al. [18]. Air quality forecasting information from the National Research Council is used to improve the sensitivity of air monitoring instrument, affected by atmospheric scattering and surface emissions due to thermal radiation by Martin [19]. The explored effects of air pollutant such as PM in urban form and haze pollution in China using the experimental result used in predicting the impacts of haze pollutions, which threatens the human life by Yuana et al. [20]. The ozone monitoring instruments and kalman filter is used to estimate nitrogen oxide emission and its impacts by comparing measured emission values with satellite data by Metia et al. [21]. To evaluate surface temperature, normalized difference surface index and normalized build up index values taken from LANDSAT images by Musses et al. [22]. The proposed spatial, temporal anomaly detection method using Sentinel 2 satellite images is used to observe heavy metal stress on rice crops by Liu et al. [23].

B. Contributions

1. Leaf samples from roadside to estimate air pollutant such as NO₂, CO, OH.
2. To study HSI relations with pollutant deposition on leaves for pollutant measurement.
3. To analyze correlation performance metrics between lab measurement values and satellite pixel-HSI values through Regression learning prediction algorithm.

C. Inferences from Literature Survey

Existing method monitors air pollutant only at particular location or area, not on the streetwise or online tracking of pollutant in the streets. The various pollutants other than automobile exhaust gases such as SO_x, NO_x, CO and CO₂ needs special methods to measure the pollutant levels such as NO, OH and requires time to measure such pollutants in the lab. Furthermore, pollutant monitoring in streetwise level and online measurement is still a challenging task.

II. METHODS

In this paper, the air pollutant values from plant leaf are calculated by the following methods to predict air quality in an online environment.

Method I: Indoor plant leaf based pollutant measurement

Method II: Outdoor plant leaf based pollutant measurement

Method III: Tree leaf region from High Resolution Satellite image is used for pollutant measurement

Method IV: Dry leaves from Roadside trees analysed through FTIR for pollutant measurement

Method V: Tamil Nadu Pollution Control Board - Air Quality Index measurement – Laboratory Values

The overview of proposed methodology is shown in Fig. 1.

The study areas are Alandur, Manali and Velachery. The above areas, Air Quality (AQ) data of National Air Quality Index (NAQI) stations are collected. Manali is highly polluted because of industries. Leaves were collected from Aegle marmelos tree at specific height of 2m, in JB Estate (Main Road and Residential Area), is tested in spectrometer for their absorbent nature towards air pollutants. Satellite images were collected from the respective study areas such as Alandur (Main Road and Ambedkar Nagar), Manali (Main Road and Mandi Road) and Velachery (Bus Stop and Lakshmi Nagar). In this world, majority of the population is affected by indoor and outdoor pollutant. Indoor air pollution varies with environment and location. In Indoor the pollution is created because of the burning of wood, coal, dung and solid fuel smoke. Outdoor air pollutant is caused due to global warming occurring in troposphere and stratosphere and ozone depletion in the stratosphere. Three major and dangerous indoor pollutants arise due to cigarette smoke, formaldehyde and radioactive radon-22 gas. Everyday people inhale toxic gases such as NO₂, CO, CO₂, PM, SO, Pb and Ozone. The inhale of above gases lead to skin irritation, mucous membranes in eyes (due to formaldehyde), cancer, immune system, nose and throat, nervous system, cardiovascular system, systematic effects on liver, kidney, gastro-intestinal system, respiratory diseases, allergy and changes in behavioral performance.

Fig. 1 Block Diagram of Proposed Methodology

D. Method I: Indoor plant leaf based pollutant measurement

In this section, the indoor pollutant is measured through leaf with plant setup as test bed. Fig. 2 shows test bed plant for measuring pollutant from fresh plant leaf. Glass chamber is used for measuring indoor pollutant and the size of the chamber is 5mx5m. In the chamber Aegle marmelos plant sapling is kept without direct sunlight illuminated in indoor environment. Artificially generated CO₂ is kept in the CO₂ chamber, so that the CO₂ pollutant are allowed to deposit on the Aegle marmelos plant leaf for further testing of deposited pollutant leaf surface. The indoor with CO₂ deposition is analyzed with Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) camera for visualizing pollutant before and after, artificial generated CO₂ deposition on leaf surface. The leaf image before exposed to CO₂ is subtracted with leaf image after CO₂ exposure to obtain only CO₂ polluted pixels as in Fig. 3.

Fig. 2 Indoor Test Bed Experimental Setup (after pollution)

Fig. 3 Image Subtraction of leaf sample

E. Method II: Outdoor plant leaf based pollutant measurement

Fig. 4a and Fig. 4b shows outdoor test bed plant for measuring pollutant from leaves. The Aegle marmelos plant sapling is kept on road close to heavy traffic and low traffic areas during peak hours such as morning and evening. In Outdoor, air pollutants from heavy vehicles deposit on Aegle plant leaf. The polluted leaf analyze with SEM camera for pollutant in leaf. The leaf image before and after exposure to outdoor air pollution is subtracted to obtain polluted pixels using MATLAB software and pixel values are calculated for CO₂.

Fig. 4a On road Test Bed
(heavy traffic area)

Fig. 4b On road Test Bed
(residential area)

F. Method III: Satellite image based pollutant measurement

This section deals with the pollutant measurement from plant leaf on the roadside through satellite image. The Fig. 5 shows satellite image of Alandur area. Temporal image of IKONOS of roadside and residential side tree species is taken for the study. The satellite image is pre-processed with Discrete Wavelet Transform (DWT) filters for removal of unwanted noise. For better identification of objects (air pollutants) present in the image, image segmentation performed such as HSI image segmentation model using Eqs.(1) (2) and (3)

$$\begin{aligned}
 I &= R + G + B & (1) \\
 H &= \frac{(G-B)}{(I-B)} & (2) \\
 S &= \frac{(I-B)}{I} & (3)
 \end{aligned}$$

where I = Intensity, H = Hue, S = Saturation, R,G,B = Red, Green and Blue band.

Fig. 5 Location: Alandur - Satellite Image (Roadside Sample)

For every pixel in the image, HSI is calculated and formulated in the Table 1. The hue, saturation and intensity is calculated separately for both the study areas such as Alandur, Velachery and Manali and some additional areas. After the image segmentation is done using HSI technique, it is classified further to extract the detailed information

from the image. The Digital Number (DN) is calculated for image and segmented to estimate polluted pixels and identify particular air pollutants present in the leaf sample through DN.

TABLE I
ANALYSIS OF HSI VALUES FROM SATELLITE TREE LEAF REGIONS

Area	Hue	Saturation	Intensity
Alandur (Road side)	0.2631	0.1484	128
Avadi (Road side)	0.1111	0.1071	168
Ambattur (Road side)	1.3333	0.0392	153
Annanur (Road side)	0.5714	0.2095	167
Manali (Road side)	0.4883	0.1287	334
Velachery (Road side)	0.3428	0.3608	194
Kotturpuram (Road side)	0.8139	0.1604	268
Guindy (Road side)	0.6800	0.1381	181
Alandur (Residential side)	0.2894	0.2248	169
Avadi (Residential side)	0.9285	0.0939	149
Ambattur (Residential side)	0.5333	0.1111	135
Annanur (Residential side)	0.8750	0.1230	130
Manali (Residential side)	0.4230	0.0830	313
Velachery (Residential side)	0.4426	0.5700	214
Kotturpuram (Residential side)	0.6904	0.2153	195
Guindy (Residential side)	0.8205	0.1368	285

G. Method IV: FTIR based pollutant measurement

This section, deals with dry leaf is collected from Alandur area, where previously the DN is analyzed for pollutant in the previous section (Method III). The Figure 6 shows the spectrum output of leaf samples measured from FTIR for measuring pollutant from leaf to predict air quality. Figure 7 shows the photographic view of FTIR instrument where the leaf samples are tested. Collected leaf samples are placed under a close atmosphere below the sample slot to avoid light and stray radiation. The quartz, glass or plastic sample platform holds a sample platform, which carries any condition (liquid, solid or powder) of the samples.

Fig. 6 Photographic View of FTIR Spectrophotometer

Samples of leaves taken from Aegle marmelos tree during peak hours of the morning and evening from the branches of trees facing the street and also from residential sides. The leaves are stored in polythene bags and dried. The preserved samples were analyzed with FTIR for pollutant measure.

Fig. 7 FTIR Spectrophotometer output of leaf sample

Figure 8 and Figure 9 shows the pollutant spectrum of leaves taken from the roadside and residential side. The figures represent wave number (cm^{-1}) in x-axis and absorbance (A) in y-axis. The band amplitude reflects both absorption and transmission of air pollutants. In this case, FTIR gives detailed information about the air pollutants such as NO_2 , CO and OH groups by recognizing specific bonds or regions of the spectrum. In order to detect the chemical properties, FTIR spectroscopy is employed to distinguish the organic, inorganic, polymeric and infrared light scan samples. The Infra Red (IR) spectrum is divided into four regions as in Figure 8 and Figure 9. The first region ranges from 4,000 to 2,500 wavenumber (cm^{-1}) and second region 2,500 to 2,000 wavenumber (cm^{-1}) and third region is 1,500 to 400 wavenumber (cm^{-1}). Each spectrum has unique characteristics peak. IR group of functions vary between 4000 and 1450 cm^{-1} . Whenever the sample strikes the IR frequency, IR spectrum is produced and configured for additional validation. Functional groups generate diverse bond absorptions and helps to understand IR spectra at various sites and strengths. The area of the fingerprint is between 1450 and 500 cm^{-1} . FTIR molecular absorption is the primary focus of a molecule. Any molecule, which absorbs infrared radiation, causes frequent changes in the dipole of bond and vibration, causes stretching and bending effects. For every leaf sample, these effects generate regular patterns called spectrum correlated, with pollutant spectrum values. Specific vibrations observed in stretching and bending effects play a vital role in defining their characteristics and helps to distinguish the molecule and functional group. As the frequency of vibration increases, the force constant become larger and evaluate this frequency extension, Hooke's Law is used in FTIR. The law of Hooke interpret binding bonds as a simple harmonic oscillator which consist of two masses, connected by a spring. Hooke's law represents a relation between frequency of oscillation, atomic mass and constant binding power as in Eq. (4).

$$f = kx$$

where f is the force applied, k is spring constant and x represents extension of the material (typically in meters). The force constant, $f=5 \times 10^5$ dyne cm^{-1} for single bond, 2×10^6 for double and triple bond. Some frequency bands involve coupled vibrations in certain spectrum regions.

Fig. 8 Pollutant Spectrum (Road side Samples)

Fig. 9 Pollutant Spectrum (Residential side Samples)

The spectrum patterns provide ample knowledge of the sample being examined in the laboratory. Some O-H stretch features of alcohols were easily identified and their location and strength depends on extension of hydrogen bonding. Most of O-H stretching occurs in first region of functional group and appear as strong and broad band covering 3000 to 3700 cm^{-1} and some secondary alcohol occur in fingerprint regions. Sometimes the coupling interactions overlap to form cascaded stretching vibrations such as IR butanoic acid, C=O and O-H. CO group with stronger bond occupy the regions 1670 to 1780 cm^{-1} . C-O stretching of alcohol is similar and can distinguish the presence of ether, alcohol depends on presence and absence of C-O. Nitro compound occupy the region 1540 cm^{-1} , medium density NO_2 stretching occupy 1300 to 1400 cm^{-1} and stronger NO_2 occupy 1500 to 1600 cm^{-1}

H. Method V:TNPCB Lab Values based pollutant measurement

Environmental pollutant data obtain from the department of Tamil Nadu Pollution Control Board (TNPCB). Air Quality Index (AQI) categories fixed by Government for every pollutant and data obtained for experimental analysis.

III. AIR POLLUTANT MEASUREMENT

The characteristics of the spectrum such as shape, intensity and bond enables to identify the pollutant from leaf. For example, for wavelength of 3277.61 cm^{-1} and radiation absorbance of 0.04 A, the peak has stronger intensity and inferred as X-H bond with functional group O-H [Robert M. Silverstein, Francis X. Webster and David J. Kiemle]. Using this functional group, pollutant is identified as alcohol. The process is repeated for all the peaks present in the spectrum to identify the type of pollutant from leaf. Table 2 and Table 3 shows three X-H bonding for both roadside and residential leaf sample data, with different wave numbers such as 2917.89 cm^{-1} and 2849.68 cm^{-1} .

TABLE II
SPECTRUM ANALYSIS RESULT OF DRY LEAVES OBTAINED THROUGH FTIR SPECTROPHOTOMETER (ROADSIDE TREES)

S.no	Transmitted Wavelength (cm^{-1})	Radiation Absorbance (A)	Shape	Intensity	Bond	Functional Group (abbreviation)	Name of Functional Group (Pollutant)
1	3294.57	0.03	Broad	Strong	X-H	OH	Alcohol
2	2916.70	0.05	Sharp	Strong	X-H	NH	Alkyne
3	2849.09	0.04	Sharp	Strong	X-H	OH	Alcohol
4	2107.16	0.01	Broad	Weak	X = Y	C = C	Alkynyl
5	1727.70	0.03	Sharp	Strong	X = Y	C = O	Carbonyl
6	1637.56	0.03	Sharp	Weak	X = Y	C = O	Alkene
7	1462.26	0.03	Sharp	Weak	X - Y	NO_2	Nitrogen Dioxide
8	1028.04	0.11	Sharp	Weak	X - Y	OH	Secondary Alcohol
9	529.12	0.11	Sharp	Weak	X - Y	CH	Alkane

TABLE III
SPECTRUM ANALYSIS RESULT OF DRY LEAVES OBTAINED THROUGH FTIR SPECTROPHOTOMETER (RESIDENTIALSIDE TREES)

S.No.	Transmitted Wavelength (cm ⁻¹)	Radiation Absorbance (A)	Shape	Intensity	Bond	Functional Group (abbreviation)	Name of Functional Group (Pollutant)
1	3277.61	0.04	Broad	Strong	X-H	OH	Alcohol
2	2917.89	0.04	Sharp	Strong	X-H	NH	Alkyne
3	2849.68	0.04	Sharp	Strong	X-H	OH	Alcohol
4	2102.91	0.01	Broad	Weak	X ≡ Y	C ≡ C	Alkynyl
5	1732.89	0.02	Sharp	Strong	X = Y	C = O	Carbonyl
6	1603.38	0.05	Sharp	Weak	X = Y	C = C	Aromatic
7	1375.75	0.04	Sharp	Medium	X - Y	NO ₂	Nitrogen Dioxide
8	1247.96	0.04	Sharp	Weak	X - Y	C - N	Phenol
9	1032.74	0.06	Sharp	Strong	X - Y	OH	Secondary Alcohol

At 1375,75 c m⁻¹, 0.04 A, the functional group is nitrogen dioxide with medium bond X-Y. Two secondary alcohols appears at 1247.96 c m⁻¹, 0.04A and 1028.04 c m⁻¹, 0.11A for two separate absorbance factor. For both frequencies at 2102 c m⁻¹, 0.01A, one three-bond stretching vibration occurs. For both roadside and industrial side collected leaf spectra, three hydrogen proton bond donors are identified, but with minor transmission shifts. From the tables, it is evident that pollutant exists less comparatively on the residential side based on the transmitted wavelength and absorbance. Such spectrum values have been identified and working group such as NO₂, CO and OH is used to measure pollutant concentrations in the study area for potential validation.

Table 4 and Table 5 shows the DN values of three pollutants taken for study. The analysis is carried out for each day as planned for data collection of both roadside and residential side samples.

TABLE IV
DN VALUES OBTAINED FROM ROADSIDE TREE LEAF REGIONS FOR THE AIR POLLUTANTS ON SELECTED DATE

Pollutants	DN Values			
	01-09-18	11-09-18	21-09-18	01-10-18
NO ₂	80	82	81	81
CO	87	85	88	86
OH	67	69	69	69

TABLE V
DN VALUES OBTAINED FROM RESIDENTIALSIDE TREE LEAF REGIONS FOR THE AIR POLLUTANTS ON SELECTED DATE

Pollutants	DN Values			
	01-09-18	11-09-18	21-09-18	01-10-18
NO ₂	87	88	88	85
CO	110	114	115	108
OH	81	83	83	80

In this paper, three major pollutants NO₂, CO and OH are taken for study in live pollutant measurement. Table 6 and Table 7 shows Pollutant comparison analysis of roadside and residential side data's. The three major pollutants NO₂, CO and OH taken for study is tabulated.

TABLE VI
AIR POLLUTANT LEVELS OBTAINED FROM GOVERNMENT BOARD, FTIR AND SATELLITE IMAGE (ROAD SIDE)

Pollutants	Time	Station	Government board data (microgram/cubic metre) $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$	FTIR Measured value (Leaf-collected) (Absorbance) A	Satellite Measured DN value (Road side Tree Leaf) DN values (H,S,I)
City Area					
Day 1 - 01/09/18					
Morning					
NO ₂	10:00 am	Alandur	22	0.03	H = 0.3600 S = 0.1908 I = 131
CO			52	0.04	
OH			42	0.04	
Evening					
NO ₂	05:00 pm	Alandur	21	0.03	H = 0.3333 S = 0.1363 I = 132
CO			50	0.03	
OH			47	0.04	
Day 2 - 11/06/18					
Morning					
NO ₂	10:00 am	Alandur	25	0.03	H = 0.3913 S = 0.1769 I = 130
CO			53	0.03	
OH			44	0.04	
Evening					
NO ₂	05:00 pm	Alandur	26	0.03	H = 0.4090 S = 0.1641 I = 134
CO			34	0.03	
OH			47	0.04	

TABLE VII
AIR POLLUTANT LEVELS OBTAINED FROM GOVERNMENT BOARD, FTIR AND SATELLITE IMAGE (RESIDENTIAL SIDE)

Pollutants	Time	Station	Government board data (microgram/cubic metre) $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$	FTIR Measured value (Leaf-collected) (Absorbance) A	Satellite Measured value (Residential side Tree Leaf) DN values (H,S,I)
Residential Area					
Day 1 - 01/09/18					
Morning					
NO ₂	10:00 am	Alandur	20	0.03	H = 0.2894 S = 0.2209 I = 172
CO			38	0.04	
OH			42	0.04	
Evening					
NO ₂	05:00 pm	Alandur	20	0.03	H = 0.3076 S = 0.2321 I = 168
CO			40	0.03	
OH			45	0.04	
Day 2 - 11/09/18					
Morning					
NO ₂	10:00 am	Alandur	22	0.03	H = 0.3170 S = 0.2383 I = 172
CO			40	0.04	
OH			43	0.04	
Evening					
NO ₂	05:00 pm	Alandur	22	0.03	H = 0.1818 S = 0.1964 I = 168
CO			42	0.04	
OH			47	0.03	

I. Regression Analysis for Online AQI Measurement

The regression analysis is performed for the variables such as pollutant levels of OH, NO₂ and CO collected from pollution control board, pollutant deposition level in leaf collected from roadside, indoor and outdoor plant through FTIR, HSI values from satellite tree leaf regions. In this paper, pollutant levels collected from pollution board department is taken as dependent variable (Y) and pollutant levels obtained from FTIR through dry leaves, SEM

camera images, satellite images tree leaf region as (X) variable. Table 8 shows the pollutant level from the pollution board and in the same location, satellite images obtained for roadside tree leaves to calculate HSI.

TABLE VIII
POLLUTANT LEVEL AND SATELLITE PIXEL OBTAINED FROM ROADSIDE TREE LEAVES

Pollutant Level government data Vs Satellite measured level - 19/05/2020 (Roadside)					
Location	Pollutant	Pollutant Level	Satellite Data		
			Hue	Saturation	Intensity
Alandur	OH	21	0.2631	0.1484	128
	NO ₂	10			
	CO	24			
Manali	OH	79	0.4883	0.1287	334
	NO ₂	38			
	CO	42			
Velachery	OH	30	0.3428	0.3608	194
	NO ₂	7			
	CO	55			

J. Neural Network

The neural network identifies relationship among a set of data as such like the human brain. For any changing inputs, the best result is obtained by the network without redesigning process by recognizing correlation and hidden patterns. The best line of fit identified through regression is trained to obtain better correlation. The training function NET.trainFcn along with NET.trainParam performs training using two train argument format such as matrices and cell arrays. Both formats helps to train and simulate the network data. Parallel Computing Toolbox enables to perform training faster even on a larger dataset. From the comparison result of pollutant level government data and other methods such as indoor-outdoor leaf pollutant, satellite and FTIR measurement level, it is evident that regression value predicted for the pollutants OH, NO₂ and CO is not optimal. So, for better regression, the network is further trained using feed-forward back propagation neural network training function. The result obtained after a trained neural network enables to develop an effective tool for analyzing and predicting the behaviour of air pollutants. Based on the Regression analysis comparison after trained neural network, it is concluded that OH is best correlated with Saturation, CO with Hue and NO₂ with Intensity data.

K. Ground Truth Verification

The best-correlated satellite data after training the network is taken for ground truth verification. Table 9 depicts the ground truth analysis of all three air pollutants for a particular day of roadside tree leaf samples.

TABLE IX
GROUND TRUTH ANALYSIS (25/08/2020)

Pollutant	AQI from government lab	Satellite data	Regression	Satellite AQI calculated using Regression
OH	46	0.369	$y = 267.24(H) - 4.139$	44.472
NO ₂	11	0.251		12.938
CO	21	0.270		18.015

IV. CONCLUSIONS

In India, Air pollutant level for a particular area is measured and displayed in website of pollution control board and never display for road-wise or streetwise pollutant level. However, the prediction of air quality in streetwise and road-wise is a challenging task. In this paper, we measure AQI through satellite image of tree leaf region, HSI is calculated. The HSI is correlated with the pollution level displayed in the website. The pollution board website displays AQI only for major city areas such as Velachery, Manali and Alandur. Such area pollutant levels are taken for the proposed study and correlated to the satellite image leaf region area HSI and the pollutant level from FTIR values. Initially, Regression learning algorithm predicts the pollution level for the known area in this study and modelling extends the prediction for the roadside pollutant level and street level pollution measurement. For the ground truth verification road and street wise pollution deposition and level is obtained from the leaf in indoor and outdoor as discussed in the method I and II. Potted plants were placed on the roadside for a day and the leaves were tested through SEM images for pollution level measurement as discussed in the method II. The same potted plant placed in the indoor environment and measured for the pollutant level as per method I. The pollutant level measured from the leaf of both indoor and outdoor proves with high correlation between the leaf based pollutant level and calculated AQI for that particular environment. Furthermore, the leaf pollutant level measurement from satellite image is ground truth verified through the experimentation of pollution level measurement from indoor and outdoor plant leaf pollutant level measurement. However the pollutant measurement through FTIR and dry leaf is highly correlated to the AQI values from website. For FTIR pollution level measurement needs minimum of one to two hour to display the pollutant level after collecting the dry leaf from the particular area of pollutant level measurement. Moreover the satellite image based pollutant measurement can measure the levels through regression modelling at the instant is more useful for the human and avoids the movement in the roadside, where pollutant level is high. The pollutant level from satellite image also helps the traffic department to divert the traffic on the roads where the pollution level is low. Furthermore, the research can also be extended for identification of other pollutants such as SO₂, CO₂ and PM10 through deep learning and sensor systems.

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The information was gathered from the website of the Central Pollution Control Board of India (<https://app.cpcbccr.com/AQI India/>).

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